

The Austrian Baroque Corpus

ABaC:us – Austrian Baroque Corpus, Claudia Resch and Ulrike Czeitschner (eds.), 2015.

<http://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/> (Last accessed 01.11.2017) Reviewed by Annika Rockenberger (University of Oslo, Norway), [annika.rockenberger \(at\) ub.uio.no](mailto:annika.rockenberger@ub.uio.no)

Abstract

ABaC:us Austrian Baroque Corpus is a small scale linguistic as well as literary corpus of five works by Austro-German Baroque cleric, preacher and writer Abraham a Sancta Clara in Older New High German. The transcribed, TEI-P5-encoded and PoS-annotated full-texts are presented alongside digital facsimiles, containing 1,000 pages in print or 200,000 tokens.

Introduction

ABaC:us – Austrian Baroque Corpus is a small project initiated and led by linguist Claudia Resch at the Department for Corpus Linguistics and Text Technology at the Austrian Academy of Sciences as early as 2010. Stemming from an earlier research project funded by the city of Vienna that has been significantly expanded afterwards, it provides in its current form a carefully selected digital collection of prose texts from the Austro-German Baroque era (ca. 1650–1750) in the historical Older New High German, thematically mainly concerning the contemporarily popular topics of *Ars Moriendi* (the ‘Art of Dying Well’ according to Christian precepts), *Dance of Death* and *Memento Mori* (‘remembering that one has to die’) in literature. The corpus features the five main works by Austrian cleric and preacher Abraham a Sancta Clara (1644–1709)¹ on said topics in the form of digital facsimile, machine-readable as well as human-readable transcriptions, and with linguistic annotations.

As of 2015, preliminary results of the project, including a part of the initial text corpus, are freely available via an interactive, web-based application for researchers and the general public on the project's website, hosted by the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Abraham_a_Sancta_Clara (last accessed 01.11.2017).

Content

The corpus (ca. 1,000 pages of printed text or 200,000 tokens) consists of the first editions of the five main works written by or attributed to Abraham a Sancta Clara:

Abraham a Sancta Clara: Mercks Wienn. Vienna, 1680.

<https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/get/abacus.1>

Abraham a Sancta Clara: Lösch Wienn. Vienna, 1680.

<https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/get/abacus.5>

Abraham a Sancta Clara: Grosse Todten Bruderschaft. Vienna, 1681.

<https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/get/abacus.7>

Abraham a Sancta Clara: Augustini Feuriges Hertz. Salzburg, 1693.

<https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/get/abacus.9>

Abraham a Sancta Clara: Todten-Capelle. Würzburg, 1710.

<https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/get/abacus.3>

The criteria for the selection of texts for the corpus were the following:

Media: printed books

Period: literary Baroque (ca. 1650–1750)

Language: Older New High German (Southern German / Austrian region)

Genre: devotional-theological literary prose

Confession: post-reformation Roman-Catholic

Author: Abraham a Sancta Clara (known and/or attributed)

Topic: Christian dealing with death and dying

Even though the creation of the corpus – as a reference corpus of Older New High German – was done with linguistic annotation and later use by language historians in mind, the criteria for selecting texts to build the corpus instead seem to follow literary and cultural-historical parameters by choosing only texts by one author from one cultural-religious region and one genre. These criteria might be inherited from the 2010 literary-historic project by Hubert Christian Ehalt that lay the textual foundation for the ABaC:us corpus. The main selection criterion – texts in Older New High German (ONHG) – stated on the project website is the critical selection factor, though: ONHG is one of the less documented and linguistically

researched historical variations of German. So far, ABaC:us is the only reference corpus explicitly dedicated to ONHG from the Austro-German region, while other linguistic corpora of written German with a historical perspective² often under-represent this linguistic variation. The entire corpus can be downloaded as a .zip-file in the XML/TEI-P5 text encoding format from the project's website <https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/abacus-data.zip>. Unfortunately, texts cannot be downloaded individually, nor is an API provided. All texts of the corpus can be read, queried, and explored via the web-based application built with the Corpus Shell modular framework.³

Scope of the Corpus and Linguistic Annotations

The scope of the ABaC:us corpus is two-fold: the editors want to provide a linguistically annotated (small) reference corpus of ONHG texts with full functionality, and they want to provide the individual texts in the corpus as digital scholarly editions in a readable, easily accessible manner while staying as true as feasible to the historical textual material. The focus is explicitly on the linguistic annotation and preparation of the corpus and its use in linguistic research. The philological part of the corpus is thus kept to a minimum standard: textual criticism is made where ‘obvious mistakes’ are found in the text and corrected accordingly with the original being held in the transcription and the correction being displayed interlinear in a smaller, red font. Individual justifications for corrections or alternatives are not provided.⁴ The corpus is decidedly not intended for specialised historical-philological and literary purposes; it is meant to provide the texts in a manner true to the original first edition so that they are readable in modern

² To name just one example: The German Text Archive (Deutsches Textarchiv) provides a reference corpus of written New High German from 1601–1901, where the majority of texts included are post 1771 or pre 1661, thus under-representing ONHG. See the second graph at <http://www.deutschestextarchiv.de/doku/textauswahl> (last accessed 04.01.2018).

³ https://clarin.oeaw.ac.at/ccv/corpus_shell (last accessed 01.11.2017). Corpus Shell is a modular framework for displaying and querying linguistic data developed at the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities in the CLARIN-ERIC infrastructure.

⁴ Annotation principles and editorial guidelines (in German) are provided here <https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/index.html?x-format=html&path-detail=content%2FAnnotation.xml> (last accessed 04.01.2018).

typography as well as in their historical typography and layout by use of digital facsimiles that accompany the transcriptions.

However, the philologically inclined user will find the following features retained in the edition:

Ortho-typographical information is largely kept: *i* and *j*, as well as *u* and *v*, are retained unchanged. Caps, initials and the shifting between *Fraktur* and *Roman* type as well as boldface and italics are retained, too

Ligatures are kept if and only if there is a Unicode character for it

Historical Umlauts are kept, however, Umlaut with e-superscript is transcribed with the modern equivalents ä, ö, ü

The difference between long-s *f* and round-s *s* is not retained

Paratextual information – like headers, ornaments, footwork incl. catchwords – is retained

Textual macrostructure (headings, subheadings, paragraphs etc.) is retained

It should be noted that since the ABaC:us reference corpus understands itself first and foremost a linguistic resource, there is neither a philological or bibliographical description of the edited texts in the corpus nor are any of the texts enriched with literary-historical commentary.

The heart of ABaC:us is the linguistically annotated text corpus of the five works by Abraham a Sancta Clara. Due to it being a non-standard language corpus, linguistic tagging was first done automatically using the Stuttgart-Tübingen-TagSet⁵ (automatic linguistic tagging tools are designed for modern, standardised languages while ONHG is close, but not entirely similar to, New High German so that automatic tagging results in quite a few false positives), and then manually checked and adjusted to match the historical ONHG variant. The corpus of 200,000 tokens can be browsed by five pre-defined linguistic indexes

<https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/corpus.html>:

Wortformen (form of words) – listing alphabetically 22,835 distinct words

Lemmata – listing alphabetically 13,505 distinct lemmata

Wortarten (part of speech PoS) – listing 82 PoS tags according to the

Stuttgart-Tübingen-TagSet (150,620 items), with two additional lists of contracted forms that are not covered in the Stuttgart-Tübingen TagSet

⁵ <http://www.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/Elwis/stts/stts.html> and <http://www.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/resources/stts-1999.pdf> (last accessed 01.11.2017).

Personennamen (person names) – listing alphabetically 1,013 person names in three categories: biblical names, historical names, mythological names

Ortsnamen (place names) – listing alphabetically 346 place names in five geographical categories: mountains, bodies of water, regions/countries/continents, streets and town squares in Vienna, other towns and villages

The interface also has an integrated search function, where a full-text search can be done looking for individual words, phrases and combinations of words. Additionally, an index search can be done explicitly looking for word form, lemma, PoS, person and place names. The meticulous linguistic tagging and the Corpus Shell framework allow for rather complex queries: Thus, the website has an entire page dedicated to a ‘how to...’ of searching and browsing the corpus: <https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/index.html?path-detail=content/Nutzung.xml> (last accessed 01.11.2017).

Usage

Navigation

ABaC:us is one of the few text collections of early modern German language and literature and with the editors' choice of linguistic material and annotation indeed breaking new grounds. However, the affection of the editorial team for their content – shown in the use of clippings from the digital facsimiles of the original texts in the navigational menu and as headings and subheadings – is on a first glimpse cute but quickly becomes frustrating. What hides behind the obscure labels and signs can only be imagined (or must be found out by trial and error). It took me several visits to the website and a lucky mistake before I found out that the layout of the interface can be changed by using a mouse-over menu hidden behind the image of a typographical rose in the far right corner of the navigational menu.

[Image_Menu_MBAir]

ABaC:us – works like a Home button, the front page of the website

Corpus – serves as the ‘About’ page with general information on the collection

Menfch! probier es – browsing and reading interface

Annotation – a page with the editorial guidelines

Nutzbarkeit – a page with information on intended audiences and querying the corpus

merckts wohl – a page with citation information, download area and a short list of publications on and about the ABaC:us corpus

uffber vns – the ‘impressum’ with contact information and names of editors

Danck! – a page with acknowledgements

linck/ – a pop-up window with a stable link to the site you're on

⊗ – a mouse-over menu for selecting three different layouts for the interface

Reading the texts

The ABaC:us corpus decidedly provides readable – and self-acclaimed reader-friendly – texts of the five main works of Abraham a Sancta Clara both in transcription with modern typography and in a digital facsimile of the first printed editions. The interface layout can be adjusted (by selecting one of three layout options via a menu hidden behind a typographical rose to the far right of the navigation pane) to fit the users' screen. I have attempted reading the texts on the project website⁶ with different hardware setups, and the user experience was somewhat different.

The ‘laptop version poses some minor difficulties. In the preset layout (‘automatic’ / ‘Layout 3’) for the reader-view, the text area on the right side is not scalable at all and always displays the transcription plus the digital facsimile side by side. In contrast, the navigation area expands over the entire left side. This arrangement results in a view where the text and facsimile of the edition are squeezed into the right half of the screen while the left navigational side is mainly blank space. The best view for this hardware setup is – in my opinion – ‘Layout 2’:

⁶ Some technical info: I have used a 13.3" MacBook Air (early 2015 edition), with a 1440 × 900 display and an Intel HD Graphics 6000 1536 MB, using macOS Sierra and the latest version of the Google Chrome web browser. I have tried using the website with a smartphone (iPhone 6), the menus are hard to navigate due to too small fonts. The reader-view is non-scalable on the smartphone screen either, especially since the facsimiles retain their original size.

Austrian Baroque Corpus x Annika
 https://acdh.oew.ac.at/abacus/corpus.html

BaC:us Corpus Mensch! probier es Annotation Nutzbarkeit merckts wohl über ons Dank! linc/

Register
 Wortformen
 Lemmata
 Wortarten
 Personennamen
 Ortsnamen

Bücher
Mercks Wienn
 Werk Inhalt Metadaten

Titel
 v. Umschlag recto / v. Umschlag verso / v. fliegendes Vorsatzblatt recto / v. fliegendes Vorsatzblatt verso / Abb. vor Titel recto / Leerseite / Titel recto / Titel verso

Dedicatio
 Widmung [S. 1] / Widmung [S. 2] / Widmung [S. 3] / Widmung [S. 4] / Widmung [S. 5] / Widmung [S. 6] / Widmung [S. 7] / Widmung [S. 8] / Widmung [S. 9] / Widmung [S. 10]

Imprimatur
 Imprimatur
 Leerseite

Lieber Leser
 1 / 2 / 3 / 4 / 5 / 6 / 7 / 8 / 9 / 10 / 11 / 12

Entwurf des sterblichen Lebens
 13, Abb. / 14 / 15 / 16 / 17 / 18 / 19 / 20 / 21 / 22 / 23 / 24 / 25 / 26 / 27 / 28 / 29 / 30 / 31 / 32 / 33 / 34 / 35 / 36 / 37 / 38 / 39 / 40 / 41 / 42 / 43 / 44 / 45 / 46 / 47 / 48 / 49 / 50 / 51 / 52 / 53 / 54 / 55 / 56

Tod / Geistliche
 57, Abb. / 58 / 59 / 60 / 61 / 62 / 63 / 64 / 65 / 66 / 67 / 68 / 69 / 70 / 71 / 72 / 73 / 74 / 75 / 76 / 77 / 78 / 79 / 80 / 81 / 82 / 83 / 84 / 85 / 86 / 87 / 88 / 89 / 90 / 91 / 92 / 93 / 94 / 95 / 96 / 97 / 98 / 99 / 100 / 101

Suchet
 ihr findet

auff die Seiten
 Mercks Wienn, S. 72

* (72) *

Was ist würdiger / als der Seraphische Orden deß Heiligen Francis=ci? Jener Blinde / welchem der Heyland mit so wunderlicher Manier das Gesicht erstatt / in dem er ihme eine durch Speichel befeuchtigte Erden an die Augen gerieben / welches sich dem Menschlichen Vrtel nach so wenig reimbte / als ein Faust auff ein Aug / als er von Christo gefragt worden / was er sehe / gabe ein artliche Antwort. Video homines velut arbores, &c.

Jch sihe die Leuth wie die Baumer da=her gehen / diser Blinde hat nicht übel von der Farb geredt / dann in aller Warheit seynd wir Menschen dem Bäumern ähnlich vnd dem Holtz / dessen Natur ist / das es alzzeit oben schwimbt im Wasser / also seynd wir Menschen gesitt vnd gesind / daß wir nur nach Höhe trachten / dahero der Welt ihr Praedicata sich mehristen Theil / auff die Berg retiriren / vnd wil niemand anderst als Back von

Backs=

Was ist würdiger / als der Seraphische Orden deß Heiligen Francis=ci? Jener Blinde / welchem der Heyland mit so wunderlicher Manier das Gesicht erstatt / in dem er ihme eine durch Speichel befeuchtigte Erden an die Augen gerieben / welches sich dem Menschlichen Vrtel nach so wenig reimbte / als ein Faust auff ein Aug / als er von Christo gefragt worden / was er sehe / gabe ein artliche Antwort. Video homines velut arbores, &c.

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Backs.

Zitation: Abraham à Sancta Clara: Mercks Wienn, Wien, 1680. (Digitale Ausgabe) S. 72. In: ABaCus – Austrian Baroque Corpus. Hrsg. von Claudia Resch und Ulrike Czetzschner. <https://acdh.oew.ac.at/abacus/get/abacus.1.92> abgerufen am 6. 11. 2017

[Image_ReadingView_MBAir].

‘Layout 1’ will horizontally stack the panes so that the text area ends up at the bottom, and one has to scroll down/up with every page turn.

Austrian Baroque Corpus x Annika
 https://acdh.oew.ac.at/abacus/corpus.html

BaC:us Corpus Mensch! probier es Annotation Nutzbarkeit merckts wohl über ons Dank! linc/

Register
 Register [S. 1] / Register [S. 2] / Register [S. 3] / Register [S. 4]
 Leerseite / Leerseite / Leerseite / h. fliegendes Vorsatzblatt recto / h. fliegendes Vorsatzblatt verso / h. Umschlag recto / h. Umschlag verso

Lösch Wienn
 Werk Inhalt Metadaten

Todten Bruderschaft
 Werk Inhalt Metadaten

Augustini Feuriges Hertz
 Werk Inhalt Metadaten

Todten-Capelle
 Werk Inhalt Metadaten

Suchet
 ihr findet

auff die Seiten
 Mercks Wienn, S. 72

* (72) *

Was ist würdiger / als der Seraphische Orden deß Heiligen Francis=ci? Jener Blinde / welchem der Heyland mit so wunderlicher Manier das Gesicht erstatt / in dem er ihme eine durch Speichel befeuchtigte Erden an die Augen gerieben / welches sich dem Menschlichen Vrtel nach so wenig reimbte / als ein Faust auff ein Aug / als er von Christo gefragt worden / was er sehe / gabe ein artliche Antwort. Video homines velut arbores, &c.

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Backs.

[Image_ReadingView_Layout1_MBAir]

In the automatic layout, the side-by-side view of transcription and facsimile doesn't align entirely, so that automatic line breaks appear in the transcribed text that elongate the text so that scrolling down and up inside the reader-view becomes necessary. Additionally, the mouse-over function where the PoS tags and lemmata appear in a grey panel above the transcribed text makes the narrow transcription pane even less readable. The citation information underneath the reader-view clutters the right side of the interface even more. Additionally, I have viewed the website on a desktop computer with a 24" screen⁷ where the Corpus Shell interface can be adjusted to fit all four panes without cropping images or breaking lines in the transcribed texts. Here, the text of all panes is easily accessible, readable from a standard distance, and the facsimiles are visible in full size, as well as the navigational panel on the far left and the search pane on the middle-left side.

The screenshot displays the BaC:us website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the logo 'BaC:us' and several menu items: 'Corpus', 'Mensch! probier es', 'Annotation', 'Nugbarkeit', 'merckts wohl!', 'über ons', and 'Dank!'. Below the navigation bar, the main content area is divided into several sections. On the left, there is a 'Registrier' section with various links and a search bar. In the center, there is a 'Suchet' section with a search bar and a list of search results. On the right, there is a 'Mercks Wienn, S. 58' section with a facsimile image of a historical document. The facsimile image shows a page with a decorative border and text in German, including the heading 'Der Todt hat auch ein ziemliche Anzahl der Geistlichen in der Wiennstadt zur Ewigkeit befürdert.' and a large initial 'D'.

[Image of interface with both panes active in laptop setup Image_Interface_HP24]

⁷ I have used the Hewlett Packard EliteDisplay E242 24" screen (1920 × 1200) with full HD resolution and a Mac Mini (late 2014 edition) with an Intel Iris 1536 MB graphics card, running macOS El Capitan and the latest version of the Google Chrome web browser.

However, I believe that instead of squeezing the transcription and facsimile plus the navigational pane and the search in one view (regardless of the layout choice), it would have been less convoluted and more user friendly to have a transcription only view (with an optional facsimile in parallel) in the reader-view.⁸

Querying the corpus

It seems to me that the search-and-query-view is the initially intended view for the ABaC:us project. Exploring the corpus with specific searches and using parallel view functions to glance at the contextual information makes sense. Thus, the reader-view is a sub-ordinated view for the search pane (in the middle), where readability is not as crucial.

Since the editors themselves have shown in several articles how the corpus querying using the functions of the Corpus Shell framework can lead to new insights in historical-linguistic research, especially of ONHG,⁹ I will confine myself to a brief overview.

Queries can be done either by full-text searches via the search field (words, phrases and combinations of words) or by using the index search. Combinations can become quite elaborate; thus, the website has an overview of the how-to on the ‘Nutzbarkeit’-page (usage). Results of queries are given chronologically (publication date of the work) and list the frequency of the word or phrase etc., in question. The results are also shown in a keyword in context view with the search term highlighted in bold font. By clicking on the individual result, the transcribed text plus facsimile are shown for more context.

Results of queries, however, cannot be downloaded as data sets.

Conclusion

All in all, the ABaC:us – Austrian Baroque Corpus provides a reliable and expandable resource for linguistic material from a widely neglected linguistic area and time. With the editors choice of a single but representative author of late Austrian Baroque, a thematic scope focusing on

⁸ The Deutsches Textarchiv <http://www.deutschestextarchiv.de> (last accessed 01.11.2017), for example, has the optional views function where one can chose between a variety of views of the edited text and parallel presentations.

⁹ Resch/Dressler 2016.

roman-catholic devotional practice and the full-text transcription and digital facsimiles of five complete works, the corpus serve as a viable resource for philological, historical as well as theological studies, too. Providing the meticulously encoded and annotated XML/TEI P5 files of the entire corpus free of charge in an easy to handle and share format (.zip) will enable re-use of the material and its integration into larger corpora. Hopefully, the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities, which is hosting the ABaC:us website and content, and the Austrian Academy of Sciences that has provided funding for the project will ensure long term archiving; so far, no information on future curation and archiving is given on the project's website. A summary of the project's scope and a querying manual in English would secure the use of this corpus beyond the German-speaking scientific community.

References

Claudia Resch, Wolfgang U. Dressler: Zur Pragmatik der Diminutive in frühen Erbauungstexten Abraham a Sancta Claras. Eine korpusbasierte Studie. In: Linguistische Pragmatik in historischen Bezügen. (= Lingua Historica Germanica 9). Berlin/Boston 2016, 235–250.

Archived Links

<https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/get/abacus.3>

<http://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abac>

<http://www.deutschestextarchiv.de>

<http://www.deutschestextarchiv.de/doku/textauswahl>

<http://www.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/Elwis/stts/stts.html>

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<https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/get/abacus.7>

<https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/get/abacus.9>

<https://acdh.oeaw.ac.at/abacus/index.html?path-detail=content/Nutzung.xml>

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